

Representation of Japa (Emigration) and Bad Leadership in Selected Nollywood Films

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Abstract

Background: In recent times, emigration in Nigeria has become popular in global migration discourses. This emigration is reflected in Nollywood films, and as a result, this research hinges on the fact that Nollywood is an effective tool for mirroring japa (emigration) among Nigerian youths.

Objective: The study's objective was to establish the connection between emigration, bad leadership, and postcolonial theory in the selected Nollywood films.

Methodology: This study applies a postcolonial theory in a descriptive research design that employs qualitative data collection and analysis, using the four films as the data sources. The films were The Esiris' *Eyimofe*, Dika Ofoma's *A Japa Tale*, Kola Olatunji's *Kanaani*, and Kunle Afolayan's *Ijogbon*.

Results: This paper successfully correlates Nigerians' harsh living conditions caused by bad leadership with their motivation to Japa (emigrate). The study reveals that selected films reflect the harsh realities of the country's downturn, which fuels the postcolonial hangover that drives young Nigerians to their destinations, Europe and America, despite realising the master-servant relations that Africans must endure in developed nations.

Conclusion: The conclusions drawn underscore that Nollywood filmmakers are storytellers and social critics adept at articulating the motivations that fuel the japa syndrome among Nigerian youths.

Unique contribution: The study comprehensively analyses the selected Nollywood films, connecting bad leadership and the penchant for Japa.

Key recommendation: The study recommends actively engaging Nollywood films' range of emigration narratives and examining how they mirror and influence Nigerian youths' perceptions of Japa.

Keywords: Leadership, Nollywood, emigration, japa, post-colonial

Introduction

Migration is the movement of people from one geographical location to another (Nwosu et al. 2022). When this movement is done outside a country, it is called emigration. Emigration is commonly interchanged with the word japa in Nigeria, though both words do not mean precisely the same thing. Japa combines two Yoruba words, “ja”, which means to escape, and “pa”, which in this context refers to the intensity of the escape and the air of finality. The precise moment when japa started referring to emigration cannot be accurately determined; however, the earliest prominent use of the term within popular media can be attributed to the Nigerian artiste Naira Marley's 2018 song, "Japa" (Adetayo, 2023).

The word is rooted in young Nigerians' longing to leave the country for good. Dakuku's (2022) survey revealed that seventy per cent of Nigerians are willing to japa if presented with the opportunity. (Nwosu et al., 2022) corroborated this by referring to the 2021 report of the International Migration Institute, noting that over a million Nigerians reside outside the country, and the exact number is unknown. It might be higher as a result of undocumented migrants. While mindful of the above discussions of japa provided by different scholars, this study defines Japa as the escape of Nigerians from Nigeria to other countries to search for greener pastures, to escape Nigeria's harsh economic and security realities without any intention of returning.

Sadiq and Tsourapas (2021) suggested that there is a high emigration rate in countries that arose from the aftermath of imperial and colonial control across the Middle East and sub-Saharan Africa. Nigeria is not exempted from this postcolonial experience. Since Nollywood films are a medium through which societal issues in Nigeria are mirrored, the japa trend is also mirrored in these films. Despite the large number of Nollywood films produced yearly, there has been limited scholarly attention to the postcolonial literary analysis of Nollywood films that focus on japa narratives and their exploration of bad leadership in Nigeria. This study thus examines four Nollywood films and their reflection of japa and the leadership question in Nigeria from a postcolonial lens. The four Nollywood films are Arie Esiri and Chuko Esiri's *Eyimofe* (2020), Dika Ofoma's *A Japa Tale* (2023), Kola Olatunji's *Kanaani* (2023), and Kunle Afolayan's *Ijogbon* (2023).

The uniqueness of this study lies in its interdisciplinary approach, merging film studies, postcolonial theory, leadership studies and emigration studies, with a specific focus on the Japa phenomenon as represented in Nollywood films. This study provides a scholarly platform for interrogating these films and Nollywood's contribution to the Japa narratives and leadership studies. Japa is widely discussed in Nigeria, but its representation in films has not yet received substantial academic attention. This study bridges that gap, adding depth to Nigeria's emigration studies, literary studies, leadership studies, and film scholarship. In doing so, it creates a scholarly

platform for analysing how Nollywood portrays emigration and bad leadership, thereby providing a fresh perspective on a discourse that is often examined from a purely sociological or economic angle.

Objectives of the Study

Since there has been little scholarly attention given to Arie Esiri and Chuko Esiri's *Eyimofe* (2020), Dika Ofoma's *A Japa Tale* (2023), Kola Olatunji's *Kanaani* (2023) and Kunle Afolayan's *Ijogbon* (2023) concerning emigration and bad leadership in Nigeria, this study aims to fill the gap.

The objectives of this study are to:

- a) Establish the relationship between emigration and bad leadership in these Nollywood films.
- b) Identify the connectedness between emigration and post-colonial theory in the films.

Literature Review

Factors That Fuel Japa in Nigeria

People emigrate from their home countries for different reasons, including push and pull factors (Lee, 1966). Pull factors like better job opportunities, higher wages, and better quality of life attract migrants to new areas, as individuals usually move from places of lack to places presumed to have opportunities. This study focuses on the push factors that drive japa among Nigerian youths seeking better opportunities abroad. These push factors include insufficient job opportunities, unsafe environments, economic and political instability, conflicts, and poverty (Ikuteyijo, 2020; Duruji et al., 2021). This paper establishes that other reasons Nigerian youths japa are incessant kidnappings, ritual killings, insurgency, high cost of living and inflation. Among the various factors listed, poverty and corruption emerge as salient issues and will be the central focus of this study.

It is expected that as the society experiences economic growth and increased wealth, the citizens will see a great future within their country, thereby mitigating the need to emigrate at the rate Nigerians are currently doing. Nigeria is a wealthy nation that possesses a variety of resources. This means the country can offer its citizens job opportunities, higher wages and political stability. However, these resources are mismanaged, resulting in the extreme poverty of Nigerians. Odukoya et al., (2024), (Ikuteyijo, 2020) wrote that in a study by the World Poverty Clock in 2018, Nigeria emerged as the country with the highest number of poor people in the world. It is evident, therefore, that the harder poverty bites and the population increases, the more Nigerians seek, however they can, to survive (Nwosu et al. 2022; Ikuteyijo, 2020). Japa is one of such means of survival. According to Nwosu et al., 'emigration has been a strategy employed in ancient times for human survival', which is proof that emigration did not just begin in Nigeria today. It follows that the japa trend is an escape route from the harsh realities created as a result of bad leadership in Nigeria.

Bad Leadership in Nigeria

From many quarters, it is believed that the root problem of Nigeria is the failure and irresponsibility of the people in power. In Olorok (2023), the former Minister of Education, Obiageli Ezekwesili, identified bad leadership as one of the nation's problems. Bad leadership is characterised by goals that do not support the flourishing of the citizenry of a nation (Abasilim et al., 2019). On this premise, this study defines bad leadership as the failure of leaders to faithfully and selflessly serve

their followers. Chief Nanga displays an example of bad leadership in Achebe's novel *A Man of the People* (1966), as he uses every avenue to enrich himself rather than serve the people. Like Chief Nanga, the Honourable Minister, Awogu-Maduagwu (2017) observed that Nigerian leaders' irresponsibility and lack of accountability are evident in the exploitation, oppression, greed and misuse of power. These factors have created room for the push factors such as political instability, corruption and underdevelopment in the country. This paper focuses on bad leadership as a major factor for Nigerian youths to japa from Nigeria, as seen in the four selected Nollywood films used for this study.

Nollywood Films

According to Kehinde (2008, P. 282), Nollywood is "Nigeria's movie industry by Nigerian production teams for the Nigerian people". Kehinde further maintains that Nollywood mirrors Nigerian society as it reflects the culture and highlights experiences faced by Nigerians. In 'Nollywood Babylon' (2008), a Nigerian film documentary, Lancelot Imasuen, a Nigerian film director, said Nollywood has practically become the voice of Africa. Through Nollywood, a voice has been given to the experiences of Nigerians, spanning inflationary trends, political instability, insecurity and economic downturn. The Japa Syndrome has found ample space in recent Nollywood films from this light. Nollywood is, therefore, seen as a vehicle not limited to Nigerian experiences but also African experiences on the continent and beyond.

Postcolonial Theory

Postcolonial theory emerged as a critical framework in response to the aftermath of colonialism, aiming to resist the selective forgetting of colonial legacies. This theoretical perspective, articulated by scholars such as Fanon, Spivak, Bhabha, and Said, has become the yardstick to understanding postcolonial conditions. Tyson (2015) maintains that in literary studies, postcolonial criticism serves as a subject matter and a theoretical framework, analysing literature produced by cultures responding to colonial domination. Also, postcolonial criticism addresses the lasting cultural colonisation left by colonial powers, which imposed British systems and values on the ex-colonies. This notion always makes former colonies look up to the colonial masters in virtually everything. This fuels the choice of Europe as one of the destinations for many emigrating Nigerians. In relation to this paper, Nigeria is listed among the countries that, though formally independent, may still be psychologically influenced by colonialism. This study, therefore, examines the postcolonial penchant to select European nations as locations of choice for Nigerian migrants, echoing Sadiq & Tsourapas (2021, p. 885) position that there is a high emigration rate in countries that "emerged from imperial and colonial rule – from the Middle East to sub-Saharan Africa".

Methodology

This study applied a descriptive research design employing qualitative data collection and analysis. The primary data for this study are the four Nollywood films: The Esiris' *Eyimofe* (2020), Dika Ofoma's *A Japa Tale* (2023), Kola Olatunji's *Kanaani* (2023), and Kunle Afolayan's *Ijogbon* (2023). The selected films were produced between 2020 and 2023. All data were sourced from different film streaming platforms such as Netflix, YouTube, and other internet sources. Through extensive online research, engagement with social media platforms, and recommendations from

Nollywood experts, fifteen Nollywood films that focus on the japa phenomenon were reviewed. From this pool of fifteen Nollywood films, the research selected four films that best align with the research objectives and offer the most diverse and insightful representation of the japa phenomenon. These films were chosen based on their popularity among audiences, recognition at film festivals, and the depth with which they address the japa trend. Specifically, they explore critical themes such as the societal issues driving emigration and the effects of japa on individuals. For the analysis, data were sampled based on the dialogue and characters that represent japa in the four films. The criteria for selecting the film scenes or dialogues that make up the excerpts included relevance to the study, representation of the themes, and visual symbolism. The viewing and annotation process for the data extraction included repeated viewing.

The coding process of this study involved five stages. The first stage was familiarisation. Each of the selected films was watched multiple times to gain a comprehensive understanding of their narratives, characters, and dialogues. During this stage, detailed notes were taken, focusing on moments that directly or implicitly reflected issues surrounding emigration and bad leadership. The second stage was the generation of open codes, which involved breaking down the films into smaller units of meaning, such as key scenes, quotes, and visual metaphors, and assigning labels to capture the essence of what each unit represented. Following the open coding stage, related codes were grouped into broader categories. This phase allowed the study to make connections between different codes and begin identifying overarching patterns. For instance, codes such as “corruption” were categorised under “bad governance.” This clustering helped to reveal the underlying structure of meaning across the films and provided coherence to the various narrative elements. The fourth stage involved identifying the core themes that would anchor the analysis. These themes were selected based on their frequency, relevance to the research questions, significance in advancing the study's objectives, and their alignment with the postcolonial theoretical framework guiding the study. The final stage of the coding process involved thematic interpretation, in which the identified themes were used to construct a critical analysis of the films.

This study used postcolonial theory as its guiding framework, supported by thematic and textual analysis. The films were examined within the socio-political context of contemporary Nigeria, emphasising how they represent youth emigration (japa) as a response to bad leadership.

Discussions

Bad Leadership Reflected in the Films

Bad leadership in the films is reflected in the forms of poverty and corruption.

Poverty

In the study by Adeleke et al. (2023), poverty is seen as a lack of opportunities due to social and other constraints and circumstances that inhibit living a valuable and dignified life. It also maintained that Nigeria has one of the highest populations of poor people due to bad leadership. This paper, therefore, examines the reflections of poverty as a motivation to japa in the selected Nollywood films.

Eyimofe, directed by Arie Esiri and Chuko Esiri (collectively called the Esiri brothers), centres around three characters' aspirations to travel abroad. These characters are Mofe, Rosa and Grace. The first character, Mofe, who others call "Engineer", engages in menial jobs of fixing gadgets such as generators and fridges. However, he somehow finds a way to save money to get an international passport. His dreams to japa are later crushed when his sister dies, and he has to use his savings for the burial.

Poverty is reflected in the film when Mofe's sister and her two children sleep in one room. This is typical in accommodations called "face-me-I-face-you", where low-income people reside. According to Ekhaese (2014), "Face-me-I-face-you" apartment buildings are common in major urban settlements in Nigeria. They are commonly rented to low-income residents because of their affordability. Mofe's sister and her children eventually died of suffocation from the fumes of their generator after sleeping with closed windows while the generator was running in the room. Since the public electricity supply is virtually dead or comatose, those who can afford to rely on getting electricity from generators despite the attendant challenges.

Poverty is further mirrored in *Eyimofe* through Rosa, a female character. Rosa does all she can to get herself and her pregnant sister, Grace, out of the country. We see how she keeps asking her sister, "Did you get the passport?". When Grace is reluctant, she gets upset and prods her to get it quickly. Though she shuffles between the menial jobs of hairdressing and bartending, she manages to save up for a passport.

In a scene with Auntie, she tells pregnant Grace she has to swear to hand over the baby once she is born, and Grace agrees. This shows the lengths these characters are willing to go to— exchanging a newborn's life for the "pleasures" of going to Italy. This to them is a fair deal. After she swears, the aunt asks her to swear on a totem around her neck and asks her to bring a passport, some of her pubic hair, and some blood. The characters do all these to escape the harsh realities of poverty caused by bad leadership in the country. Nothing appears to be too difficult if it facilitates their dream escape.

Rosa and Grace's dreams to japa come to an end with Grace's miscarriage. Rosa ends up "settling for less" by agreeing to marry Mr Vincent, a man who has been making romantic advances towards her. She tells Mr Vincent, "If I marry you, you will take care of my family. Grace will go to a private school, and you will open a shop for me where I will sell clothes". Grace also sells her phone to get some money. Everything the sisters do is to escape poverty and have a better life for themselves. Unfortunately, their japa plans suffer a miscarriage, just as the pregnancy.

In *Ijobon*, directed by Kunle Afolayan, poverty is also portrayed as a driving factor that fuels the characters' desire to japa. The film follows the lives and adventures of four secondary school teenagers after they stumble on a bag of uncut diamonds in their village in Oyo-Oke. In the film, there is a scene where Miss Omatshola speaks to Jamiu's father, the School Principal, about leaving the country because the salary she receives from the school is not enough. Omatshola is exasperated when the Principal promises to increase her salary from Forty Thousand Naira to Forty-five Thousand Naira. She retorts cynically:

From Forty Thousand Naira to Forty-Five Thousand Naira?

My sister is already arranging for me to join her in Germany.

The Principal, in utter helplessness at losing one of his best teachers, asks:

So, you are also joining the Japa Syndrome?

Miss Omatshola scoffing at the slight increment in her salary mirrors her disdain for the poverty and unbearable living conditions. The twelve-and-a-half per cent increase in her salary cannot meet her needs in the national inflation of the upper two digits. The only answer is to japa.

After the teacher leaves, Jamiu, who has overheard the conversation, confronts his father. He tells his father that one of his best teachers has “wisely escaped” from ending up like him. He goes on:

Father, are you not tired of poverty and suffering?
Mummy died because, as a village teacher,
you were too poor to continue her dialysis treatment.

This is reflective of the poor condition of the average Nigerian. Where there is mass unemployment, even the few employed cannot make ends meet.

Poverty is further evident in the film when the villain, Chidera, tries to get the diamonds Jamiu and his friends have stolen. She tells Banj, Ming, and Kafanchan, “In an impoverished village full of peasants, it shouldn't be too hard to find a big spender”. She says this to prove that someone who has just come in contact with precious stones would stand out in a village populated with poor people. Poverty has, therefore, become the identity of the people. Okolie & Igbini (2020) emphasised that poverty is one of the aftermaths of bad leadership in the country.

Like the characters in *Eyimofe*, Jamiu is willing to do anything to japa. When Jamiu asks how he would be able to travel, Emeka, who is meant to help him get a passport, says,

You can always go through the desert Caravan route:
From Oyo-Oke to Benin to Niger, across the desert to Mali,
then Libya. From there, cross the Mediterranean into Europe.

Furthermore, to dissuade Jamiu from going through the desert route, Oby tells him that many bad things could happen on the trip. She then asks, “

What is even chasing you? And he replies,
Oby, everything is chasing me!

By “everything”, he refers to his family’s poor living conditions, among other unpalatable circumstances.

In *Ijogbon*, the teenagers also have an internalised longing to japa to escape the suffocating poverty that dares to mortgage their future. With their Western education, they have come to understand the atrocities and misgovernance that have come to characterise leadership in the country. This has contributed in no small measure to what fuels their desire to japa from Oyo-Oke to Canada.

Likewise, *Kanaani* – the film about two lovers (Gbovo and Obehi) – mirrors poverty as a motivation for japa. One day, Obehi tells her lover that her brothers have arranged for her to travel to Italy. Gbovo gets upset and proposes an alternative: going to America. Obehi protests:

Do you have the money? I don't have money.
You don't have money. We don't have money”.

Gbovo borrows money to pay for their visas. Poverty here is reflected in the lovers' inability to afford the visa fees. Also, Gbovo's creditor seizes the family's house when Gbovo cannot repay the loan. This also mirrors Nigerians' desperation-fuelled willingness to leave the country for good, even if they have to borrow to make good their desire. Using the family house as collateral to fund their passage is common among the japa generation in Nigeria. The lovers eventually go to a church where the pastor agrees to facilitate their japa dreams at a fee. Unfortunately, he tells Gbovo that their initial payment could only cover Obehi's visa. Eventually, Obehi decides to take the trip but finds herself becoming a sex worker in Texas, and her several attempts to escape prove futile.

Gbovo and Obehi are not the only characters in *Kanaani* whose pathetic conditions fuel their japa dreams with no desire to ever return. Angela, one of Obehi's co-sex workers in Texas, is promised by her 'madam' to get her freedom within a month. Obehi is happy for her and asks what she will do after her freedom. She replies that she would find herself a white man who would help her get the green card, with which she would have permanent residency. She adds, "There's nothing there for me anymore, " meaning she is not considering returning to Nigeria, as the country has nothing to offer her.

Angela's statement shows she has lost hope in the country, which has nothing to offer her except poverty and suffering. She even says she is considering starting madam's kind of business. "... Madam is rich and influential. That's what I aspire to be". Irrespective of Madam's business being sex trafficking, Angela does not see anything wrong with it. Her longing to be wealthy by any means is traceable to the fact that while in Nigeria, she is a victim of poverty. Her craze for a permanent residency in America reflects many Nigerians' desperation to settle in foreign lands. Angela prefers the Western way of life, which informs her decision never to return to Nigeria.

Furthermore, poverty is mirrored in other characters in the film. Obehi's brothers tell her they have planned for her to go to Italy because they have heard that women are well-paid there. They say if she goes there, she will be "big" and build them a very big house. Obehi's brothers search for a better life and see their sister's emigration as a means to escape poverty.

Corruption

Corruption, in the words of Atakpa (2023), is synonymous with indiscipline that results in a state of lawlessness, which eventually paints the country in a bad light, seriously harming the economy and society as a whole. Corruption has eaten deep into the nation's fabric, such that several years into independence, Nollywood films still mirror corruption as a major issue in Nigeria.

Corruption is mirrored in *Eyimofe* when Mofe tries to fix his sister's generator, and his co-worker, Wisdom, says,

You know, most of the fuel we have here is dirty.

By “here”, Wisdom refers to Nigeria. This corroborates Nwogbo & Akhakpe's (2021) position that the resources meant to be channelled into making quality products available to the citizens are often embezzled by corrupt and greedy officials.

Furthermore, corruption is evident in the film in a dialogue between Rosa and her American boyfriend. In relating his experience at the Nigerian airport, her boyfriend explains how a Customs Officer did not search his bag but instead asked, “What did you bring for me?”. This refers to a bribe, further reflecting government officials in the parastatals' lawless and rotten state.

Like Mofe, Rosa suffers from mimicry, which partly fuels her need to japa. For instance, Rosa would rather date an American than a Nigerian. Also, when she decides to japa in her friend's aunt's house, she is in awe of the half-caste daughter in Aunt's house.

Furthermore, corruption is emphasised in the dialogue between Jamiu and his father after Miss Omatshola reveals her japa plans. When Jamiu confronts his father, telling him his mother died because his father was too poor to continue her dialysis treatment, his father responds,

Your mother died because the healthcare system was
ravidly corrupt and underfunded.

This corruption is a disease that spreads from politicians in power to civil servants working in hospitals. As a result, many Nigerians stand the risk of losing their lives due to a lack of facilities, drugs and equipment in government-owned hospitals in the country.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This paper has examined four Nollywood films, *Eyimofe* (2020), *A Japa Tale* (2023), *Kanaani* (2023), and *Ijogbon* (2023), through a postcolonial perspective. The films mirror bad leadership in Nigeria as one of the motivations of Nigerians to japa. Furthermore, these films reflect the harsh realities of the country's economic downturn, which fuels the postcolonial hangover that drives young Nigerians to their destination in Europe, despite the realisation of the master-servant relations that Africans must endure in most of Europe and the Americas. In establishing Nollywood films as efficient tools for reflecting the reality of Nigerians, this paper has successfully correlated Nigerians' harsh living conditions caused by bad leadership and their motivation to emigrate with the selected Nollywood films. In light of the findings from this study, several recommendations emerge for future research into Nollywood's depictions of emigration motivations.

First, there should be greater scholarly interest in Nollywood's productions as a veritable resource for analysing a broader range of narratives and genres that touch on emigration and other cultural, socio-economic, and political discourse. This could also reveal how the filmmakers consistently present motivations such as poor governance, corruption, and economic struggle as the bane of development in the country.

Furthermore, exploring how Nollywood's portrayal of japa might influence young Nigerians' aspirations to see the inherent dangers and illegality in choosing to japa through unorthodox means is recommended. Future research could examine whether these films, with their vivid portrayals of emigration, shape viewers' perceptions about opportunities abroad versus life in Nigeria.

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